

Figure S140. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean hourly **NO₂** volume mixing ratio (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS stations and 2021/22 for AIRNow stations.

Figure S209. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean hourly **NO₂** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS **urban** stations.

Figure S210. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean hourly **NO₂** VMR (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS **rural** stations.

Figure S143. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean hourly **NO** volume mixing ratio (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AQS and NAPS stations and 2021/22 for all NRT stations.

Figure S144. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly **HNO₃** volume mixing ratio (ppbv) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and CASTNet stations.

Figure S152. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean daily **PM_{2.5}-NO₃** concentration (µg m⁻³) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN, IMPROVE, and NAPS stations.

Figure S159. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly **NO₃** concentration in precipitation (mg L^{-1}) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

Figure S163. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly **NO₃** wet deposition (mg m^{-2}) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.